

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF THE BEAM-COLUMN JOINT ON STEEL FIBER-REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to perform a numerical analysis using the finite element method (FEM) on steel fiber-reinforced concrete (SFRC) structures, which allows evaluating the influence of the addition of steel fibers on the moment redistribution and on the behavior of the beam. The constitutive relationship of SFRC is made by means of the plastic damage model Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP), when a nonlinear behavior of the composite is adopted. To validate the applicability of the model, a numerical validation was performed, modeling and simulating in ABAQUS the beams and frames tested experimentally. In general, the numerical results indicate a good correlation with the experimental results, thus validating the methodology proposed in this work. The steel fibers increased the stiffness of the beam-column joint, leading to a change in the moment redistribution. The addition of steel fibers also allowed for the reduction of longitudinal reinforcement in the beam.

KEYWORDS: *Steel fiber-reinforced concrete, beam-column joint, numerical modelling, finite element method.*

I. INTRODUCTION

To design beam-column joint with sufficient capacity for the applied moments, it is necessary to understand the basic mechanics that occur in these regions. The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory provides the theoretical basis for the design of beam elements. The principle states that stresses and strains are linear. However, due to the inherent geometric discontinuity of these corner regions, the shear deformations have a significant effect, such that the Euler-Bernoulli hypothesis is no longer valid. Prior to cracks forming, the stresses and strains within the corner are nonlinear [1].

In reinforced concrete frames, factors such as the concrete cracking, the yield strength of steel, the arrangement of reinforcements, the reinforcement ratio, and the bond between concrete and reinforcement complicate the moment redistribution process [2]. Thus, it is essential to promote studies on moment redistribution, even though empirical equations have been proposed in various design codes [3-7].

Recent studies have reported that the contribution of moment redistribution that develops after crack formation and before reinforcement yielding is also significant and cannot be neglected [8]. Furthermore, with the application of some special materials in structural engineering, such as fiber-reinforced concrete (FRC), the moment redistribution in structures with these new materials may exhibit new characteristics [2].

The stress transfer bridging effect of randomly distributed steel fibers in concrete can increase tensile strength and delay crack propagation [9]. Additionally, the bond between concrete and reinforcement is strengthened due to the inclusion of fiber, thereby reducing the sliding of concrete compression wedges and improving shear-friction material properties [10]. As a result, the steel fiber-reinforced concrete (SFRC) elements are expected to exhibit higher stiffness and different plastic hinge properties from the ones without fibers, which leads to a change in the moment redistribution in SFRC continuous elements.

The upward trend in the use of fibers as a structural material has led to the development of various international standards providing recommendations for the design of fiber-reinforced concrete structures, such as the fib Model Code 2010 [5], ACI 544.4R [11], and RILEM TC 162-TDF [12]. In Brazil, the first technical standard related to the design of fiber-reinforced concrete structures was only published in 2021.

Despite the introduction of guidelines for the flexure and shear design of SFRC, significant restrictions exist in the applications where large plastic rotations are expected. This is due to the absence of tests demonstrating that SFRC connections can maintain their capacity during large rotations and moment redistributions. The literature presents few studies on the moment redistribution performance of SFRC elements [13].

In this context, this study aims to perform a numerical analysis using the finite element method on steel fiber-reinforced concrete structures, which allows evaluating the influence of the addition of steel fibers on the moment redistribution and on the behavior of the beam.

The paper is organized into five sections. In Section 1, the introduction provides a review of the fundamental concepts underlying the study. Section 2 presents the numerical modeling strategy, highlighting the finite elements used and the constitutive models employed. Section 3 discusses the numerical validation, comparing experimental and numerical results. Section 4 presents the results obtained for the SFRC frames. Finally, section 5 outlines the main conclusions of the research.

II. NUMERICAL MODELING STRATEGY

The numerical model was analyzed using the finite element software ABAQUS. To replicate the behavior of concrete, the Continuous Damage model available in ABAQUS, the Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, was utilized. The CDP is a model based on plasticity and damage mechanics to compute the loss of elastic stiffness of the material, characterized by two damage variables, d_t (tension damage) and d_c (compression damage).

In addition to the parameters that characterize the stress-strain relationship of the SFRC, five other parameters are required to account for the effects of multiaxial stress states in the CDP. The model includes the dilatancy angle (ψ), flow potential eccentricity (e), the ratio of biaxial to the uniaxial compressive yield stresses (σ_{b0}/σ_{c0}), the ratio between the magnitudes of deviatoric stress in uniaxial tension and compression (K_c), and the viscosity parameter (μ).

Only for the dilatancy angle, different values were adopted for reinforced concrete and SFRC. Hibbitt, Karlsson, and Sorensen [14] assert that the dilatancy angle can be interpreted as the internal friction angle of the material (\emptyset), which ranges from $32^\circ \leq \psi \leq 40^\circ$ for concrete, with 34° being the ideal value. Proença [15] determined from experimental observations, that for steel fiber-reinforced concrete, a fixed value would be suitable for the internal friction angle of this composite, with $\emptyset = 37^\circ$, and it is not directly influenced by the percentage of fibers in the composite.

The values of the plasticity parameters for the CDP were equal to: $\psi = 34^\circ$ (Reinforced concrete), $\psi = 37^\circ$ (SFRC), $e = 0.1$, $\sigma_{b0}/\sigma_{c0} = 1.16$, $K_c = 0.667$ e $\mu = 0.0001$.

2.1. Finite elements employed

The SFRC structures were modeled using the C3D8R element (linear interpolation). The quadrilateral solid element is a continuous (C), three-dimensional (3D) element with eight nodes (8) and reduced integration (R). The element has 3 degrees of freedom per node (translations in x, y, and z), capable of modeling complex geometry and performing nonlinear analyses involving contact, plasticity, and large deformations.

The longitudinal and transverse reinforcements were modeled using truss elements. The element is named T3D2, with 2 nodes, and has 3 degrees of freedom per node (translations in x, y, and z). This element can be used in two or three-dimensional analyses to model slender and linear structures that experience axial loading along the element. Figure 1 illustrates the C3D8R and T3D2 element types.

Figure 1. Element types (a) C3D8R and (b) T3D2 (adapted from Hibbitt, Karlsson e Sorensen [14]).

2.2. Constitutive models employed

To represent the reinforced concrete and the SFRC under uniaxial compression, the constitutive model for plain concrete proposed by ABNT NBR 6118 [16] was used, without accounting for potential beneficial effects of fiber incorporation. The model exhibits a nonlinear response up to the compressive strength and a linear response with constant stress up to failure.

For the tensile reinforced concrete, the constitutive model proposed by Vecchio and Collins [17] was used. The model was based on experiments conducted on reinforced concrete panels subjected to pure shear stress and it is given by Equation 1:

$$\sigma_t = \frac{f_{ct}}{1 + \sqrt{200\varepsilon_1}} \tag{1}$$

Where σ_t e ε_1 correspond, respectively, to the normal tensile stress and the tensile strain of concrete in the axial direction, and f_{ct} is the axial tensile strength of concrete.

For tensioned SFRC, the stress-strain relationship was represented using the approaches suggested by the fib Model Code 2010 [5]. The code encompasses cases where $f_{ct} > f_{Fts}$ and $f_{ct} < f_{Fts}$, with the corresponding models depicted in Figures 2(a) and (b), respectively. It is worth noting that softening post-cracking behavior was considered for the SFRC.

Figure 2. Stress-strain diagram for fiber-reinforced concrete in tension for (a) $f_{ct} > f_{Fts}$ and (b) $f_{ct} < f_{Fts}$ (adapted from fib Model Code 2010 [5]).

In Figure 2, f_{Fts} represents the serviceability residual strength of the FRC, and f_{Ftu} represents the ultimate residual strength of the FRC.

The fib Model Code 2010 [5] describes the constitutive laws of fiber-reinforced concrete under uniaxial tension by determining the residual flexural tensile strengths. These strengths are obtained through the three-point bending test on notched beams standardized by EN 14651 [18].

As the strategy of this research involved using equations to predict the flexural tensile strengths of the SFRC, it was necessary to search the literature for equations that matched the characteristics and data presented by the experiments, such as fiber type, matrix compressive strength, and fiber content applied to the matrix.

This led to the study conducted by Venkateshwaran, Tan, and Li [19]. The authors evaluated the results of three-point bending tests on 69 notched beams reinforced with steel fibers. The relationships proposed by the authors to determine f_{R1} and f_{R3} are presented in Equations 2 to 5.

$$f_{R,1} = \psi[0.320(f_{cm})^{0.5} + 6.214(RI) + 0.034N^2] \quad (2)$$

$$f_{R,3} = \psi[0.300(f_{cm})^{0.5} + 7.629(RI) + 0.373N^2] \quad (3)$$

$$\psi = (1 + l_f/100)^{0.5} \quad (4)$$

$$RI = f \frac{l_f}{d_f} \quad (5)$$

Where f_{R1} is the residual flexural tensile strength of FRC corresponding to $CMOD_1 = 0.5$ mm, f_{R3} is the residual flexural tensile strength of FRC corresponding to $CMOD_3 = 2.5$ mm, f_{cm} is the mean concrete compressive strength, f is the fiber volume fraction, l_f is the fiber length, d_f is the fiber diameter, and N is the number of hook-ends in fibers.

To demonstrate the reliability of Equations 2 and 3, the average, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation of the test-to-predicted residual flexural strengths are shown in Table 1, indicating good accuracy of the equations.

Table 1. Performance of proposed empirical equations for f_{R1} and f_{R3} (adapted from Venkateshwaran, Tan and Li [19]).

Statistical parameter	$f_{R1,TEST}/f_{R1,PRED}$	$f_{R3,TEST}/f_{R3,PRED}$
AVG	0.99	0.99
STDEV	0.18	0.17
COV	0.15	0.13

To describe the behavior of the longitudinal and transverse reinforcements, a steel material was considered with a perfect elastoplastic model having a single modulus of elasticity for both tension and compression. An elastic modulus (E_s) of 210 GPa, a Poisson coefficient of 0.3, and a maximum strain of 10‰ were assumed for the steel. The characteristic value of yield strength of reinforcing steel (f_{yk}) is 500 MPa for CA-50 steel.

III. NUMERICAL VALIDATION

3.1. SFRC beams tested experimentally by Conforti et al. (2018)

In this section, the SFRC beams tested experimentally by Conforti et al. [20] are utilized for a comparative and validation study of the predicted residual flexural strengths, the Concrete Damaged Plasticity model, and the mechanical behavior of the SFRC, as per the numerical modeling conducted.

The post-cracking properties of the SFRC were determined by predicting the residual flexural tensile strengths using the equations proposed by Venkateshwaran, Tan, and Li [19], and in accordance with the constitutive models outlined in the fib Model Code 2010 [5].

The numerical simulation adopted the parameters used by Conforti et al. [20]. The concrete exhibited a mean compressive strength (f_{cm}) equal to 43.6 MPa, tensile strength (f_{ct}) equal to 1.8 MPa, elastic modulus (E_{ci}) equal to 36976.97 MPa, and Poisson coefficient (ν) equal to 0.2. The conventional reinforcements had an elastic modulus (E_s) equal to 210 GPa and yield strength of 469.4 MPa and 562.3 MPa for the 6 mm and 10 mm bars, respectively. The steel fibers with hooked-end had a length (l_f) equal to 50 mm and diameter (d_f) of 1 mm, with fiber contents of 25 kg/m³ and 50 kg/m³.

In addition to the comparison with the results obtained experimentally by Conforti et al. [20], a comparison was also made with the numerical analysis results of Trindade [21].

It's worth noting that this work applies to concrete with a strength class of up to 45 MPa, which is more common in low and medium-rise building structures.

3.1.1. Description of beams

The beams subjected to the 4-point bending test have a width and height of 150 mm, a length of 900 mm, and a clear span of 840 mm. Figure 3 illustrates the geometry and conventional reinforcements of the beam.

Figure 3. Geometry and reinforcement details of specimens (adapted from Conforti et al. [20]).

3.1.2. Obtaining residual tensile strengths

To determine the constitutive model of SFRC under tension, it was necessary to predict the residual flexural tensile strengths f_{R1} and f_{R3} , which were obtained through Equations 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 2 provides a comparison between the predicted values and those obtained experimentally by Conforti et al. [20].

Table 2. Predicted and experimentally obtained f_{R1} and f_{R3} values.

Fiber content (kg/m ³)	f_{R1} (MPa)			f_{R3} (MPa)		
	Conforti et al. [20]	Predicted value	Δ (%)	Conforti et al. [20]	Predicted value	Δ (%)
25	3.22	3.84	19.25	2.90	4.37	50.69
50	5.08	5.05	-0.59	4.53	5.86	29.36

It can be observed that the prediction of f_{R1} was the closest to the experimental results, with the smallest differences occurring for the higher fiber content.

3.1.3. Comparative analysis of the numerical x experimental model

The comparative study was divided into two stages. In the first study, the f_{R1} and f_{R3} values found by Conforti et al. [20] were used, while in the second study, the predicted values of f_{R1} and f_{R3} were used. Regarding the characteristic length (l_{cs}), it was assumed $l_{cs} = l_f = 50$ mm.

To achieve the desired accuracy of the numerical results, a finite element mesh convergence study was conducted, evaluating force-displacement diagrams for different levels of refinement, considering approximate mesh sizes of 0.02 m, 0.03 m, 0.04 m, and 0.05 m.

Figure 4 illustrates the results of the analyses related to the first study for $V_f = 25$ kg/m³ and $V_f = 50$ kg/m³.

Figure 4. Force-displacement curve. Comparison between the first study for (a) $V_f = 25 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and (b) $V_f = 50 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

It's worth noting that, in all cases, the longitudinal reinforcements reached yielding with a maximum deformation of 10%. In the case represented by Figure 4(a), for the mesh size of 0.05 m, the onset of yielding occurred at a force of 79.78 kN and a strain of 2.70%, and the failure occurred at a force of 81.10 kN and a strain of 10%.

Figure 5 illustrates the results of the analyses related to the second study for $V_f = 25 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and $V_f = 50 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

Figure 5. Force-displacement curve. Comparison between the second study for (a) $V_f = 25 \text{ kg/m}^3$ and (b) $V_f = 50 \text{ kg/m}^3$.

The numerical models were able to predict the experimental behavior with good accuracy. However, in all configurations, the numerical results show a higher stiffness than the experimental results in the pre-peak branch, likely attributed to the definition of the elastic modulus of the SFRC. The lower experimental stiffness may also be associated with some flexibility in the supports. A similar behavior to the numerical model by Trindade [21] is observed in all mesh configurations, particularly for the finer meshes.

Correia and Barboza [22] analyzed the influence of the characteristic length on the resistance capacity of SFRC beams. By comparing the force-displacement curves for $l_{cs} = 50 \text{ mm}$ and $l_{cs} = 150 \text{ mm}$, the authors concluded that the increase in l_{cs} caused a reduction in force. The increase in characteristic length decreases the maximum deformation and, therefore, reduces the resistance capacity in the cracked regime. However, this reduction was small, reaching a maximum of 2.1%.

Finally, it can be observed that the 2nd study presented higher forces than the 1st study. This increase can be justified by the fact that the predicted residual strengths were higher than those obtained experimentally. Figure 6 illustrates the differences between the force-displacement curves of the 1st and 2nd studies for fiber contents of 25 and 50 kg/m^3 , and a mesh size of 0.05 m.

Figure 6. Force-displacement curve. Comparison between the first and second studies.

The results shown in Figure 6 also demonstrate an increase in the maximum force resisted by the beam due to the increase in the amount of added fibers to the concrete. It is also noteworthy that with the increase in fiber content, there was an increase in stiffness in the pre-peak branch. This increase occurs because the fibers delay the propagation of cracks, increasing the strength, ductility, and stiffness of the SFRC.

3.2. Reinforced concrete frame tested experimentally by Cranston (1965)

In this section, the numerical modeling of the RC frame tested experimentally by Cranston [23] was performed, with details and material properties given in Figure 7 (with dimensions in cm) and Table 3, respectively. The structure is subjected to two equally spaced incremental vertical loads applied to the beam. The modeling of the frame and the test setup in ABAQUS are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 7. Geometry and reinforcement details of frame (adapted from Cranston [23]).

Figure 8. Modeling of the frame and test setup in ABAQUS.

Cranston [23] provided only the f_{ck} and the f_{yk} , with the other data adopted based on ABNT NBR 6118 [16]. All elements of the frame have the same cross-section, with longitudinal reinforcement of diameter equal to 9.5 mm.

Table 3. Data of the materials adopted for the numerical simulation.

Concrete				Conventional reinforcement		
f_{ck} (MPa)	$f_{ct,m}$ (MPa)	E_c (MPa)	ϵ_{cu} (‰)	f_{yk} (MPa)	E_s (MPa)	ϵ_{su} (‰)
36.5	3.3	33832.53	3.5	293	210000	10

To achieve the desired accuracy of the numerical results, a finite element mesh convergence study was conducted, evaluating force-displacement diagrams for different refinement levels, considering approximate mesh sizes of 0.03 m, 0.04 m, and 0.05 m.

The curves in terms of force versus vertical displacement at the mid-span of the beam for the experimental and numerical models are illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Force-displacement curve.

The numerical models were able to predict the experimental behavior with good accuracy. However, in all configurations, the numerical results show a higher stiffness than the experimental results in the pre-peak branch, likely attributed to the definition of the elastic modulus of reinforced concrete.

The experimental model showed a maximum force of 21.9 kN, while the numerical model with a mesh size of 0.03 m reached a maximum force of 22.4 kN, resulting in a difference of 2.28%.

IV. SFRC FRAME

In this section, the numerical modeling of the Cranston frame [23] was carried out, considering the use of SFRC. The properties of the steel fibers were the same as in Conforti et al. [20] and their volumes were equal to 1% and 2%.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the effects of steel fibers on the beam when there is a monolithic connection, as well as the effects on the frame joint. For this, several cases were analyzed, where the diameter and quantity of longitudinal reinforcement of the beam were varied. Figure 10 and Table 4 present, respectively, the numbering of the longitudinal reinforcements of the beam and the analyzed configurations.

Figure 10. Numbering of longitudinal reinforcements of the beam.

Table 4. Analyzed configurations of longitudinal reinforcements of the beam.

Frame		Longitudinal reinforcement of the beam
$V_f = 1\%$	F1	Without longitudinal reinforcement
	F2	2N1 ϕ 5.0 + 2N2 ϕ 5.0
	F3	2N1 ϕ 6.3 + 2N2 ϕ 6.3
	F4	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0
	F5	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0 + 2N3 ϕ 5.0
	F6	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0 + 2N3 ϕ 6.3
	F7	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0 + 2N3 ϕ 8.0
$V_f = 2\%$	F8	Without longitudinal reinforcement
	F9	2N1 ϕ 5.0 + 2N2 ϕ 5.0
	F10	2N1 ϕ 6.3 + 2N2 ϕ 6.3
	F11	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0
	F12	2N1 ϕ 8.0 + 2N2 ϕ 8.0 + 2N3 ϕ 5.0

It is worth noting that in this analysis, CA-50 steel was considered, with the characteristic value of yield strength of reinforcing steel (f_{yk}) equal to 500 MPa.

As shown in Table 4, the SFRC frame was initially analyzed with no longitudinal reinforcement in the beam. Then, the longitudinal reinforcement was increased until the same load capacity as the reinforced concrete frame was reached, evaluated through the force-displacement curve.

To achieve the desired accuracy of the numerical results, a finite element mesh convergence study was conducted, evaluating force-displacement diagrams for different levels of refinement, considering approximate mesh sizes of 0.03 m, 0.04 m, and 0.05 m.

Figure 11 illustrates the force-displacement curves for the reinforced concrete and SFRC frames with fiber volumes of 1% and 2%, for a mesh size of 0.03 m.

Figure 11. Force-displacement curve: (a) $V_f = 1\%$ and (b) $V_f = 2\%$.

Upon analyzing Figure 11, it is observed that the F7 and F12 frames, corresponding to fiber volumes of 1% and 2%, respectively, exhibited behavior similar to the experimental model. It can be concluded that the addition of steel fibers resulted in the reduction of longitudinal reinforcement in the beam, as shown in Table 5. As the SFRC frame used steel with f_{yk} equal to 500 MPa, the longitudinal reinforcement of the reinforced concrete beam was also calculated considering f_{yk} equal to 500 MPa.

Table 5. Comparison of steel areas.

Longitudinal Reinforcement	Steel Area (cm ²)				
	RC Frame	SFRC Frame ($V_f = 1\%$)	Δ (%)	SFRC Frame ($V_f = 2\%$)	Δ (%)
Bottom	2.51 (5 ϕ 8.0)	2.01 (4 ϕ 8.0)	-19.92	1.4 (2 ϕ 8.0 + 2 ϕ 5.0)	-44.22
Top	1.51 (3 ϕ 8.0)	1.01 (2 ϕ 8.0)	-33.11	1.01 (2 ϕ 8.0)	-33.11

From the maximum bending moments (hogging and sagging) acting on the beam, as reported by Cranston [23], the resultant tensile forces in the reinforcement were calculated, with values of 63.72 kN and 94.58 kN for the top and bottom reinforcement, respectively. Subsequently, the steel areas were determined.

For the fiber volume of 2%, the reductions in the bottom and top reinforcements were equal to 44.22% and 33.11%, respectively, showing a significant reduction in conventional reinforcement. It is also noteworthy that in the region of the beam-column joint, for both fiber volumes, there was a reduction in the top reinforcement of the beam from 3 ϕ 8.0 to 2 ϕ 8.0, reducing reinforcement congestion. This reduction in reinforcements is favorable because reinforced concrete joints are critical regions for analysis and execution, due to their high steel ratio and reduced geometric dimensions.

In addition to the reduction in longitudinal beam reinforcement, a decrease in tensile damage was observed with the addition of steel fibers. Figure 12 illustrates the tensile damage in the reinforced concrete and SFRC frames with $V_f = 1\%$, for each of the analyzed configurations.

Figure 12. Tensile damage in reinforced concrete and SFRC frames with $V_f = 1\%$.

The propagation of tensile damage in the matrix shows the expected cracking pattern for the analyzed frames. The concrete starts to crack for values of $d_t > 0$, an aspect related to the development of plastic deformations under tension, which makes it increasingly less resistant until the point where SFRC no longer contributes to the tensile strength of the element and, thus, transfers the tensile stresses to the conventional reinforcement.

It is possible to perceive the importance of using longitudinal reinforcement in the beam even with the addition of steel fibers. Without it, in the frame F1 (Figure 12(b)), it is observed that the beam-column joint is functioning as a hinge, without transferring stresses and moments from the beam to the

column. With the increase of longitudinal reinforcement in the beam-column joint, there is dissipation of damage and redistribution of stresses and moments.

The development of stresses in the reinforced concrete and SFRC frames with a fiber volume of 1% is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Stresses in reinforced concrete and SFRC frames with $V_f = 1\%$.

It can be observed in the beam that the lower fibers of the cementitious matrix are under tension while the upper ones are under compression. As the loading increases, the tensile stresses in the beam evolve, highlighting the rise of the neutral axis, causing the upper fibers, between the loading points, to become increasingly compressed.

4.1. Moment-rotation curve

The behavior of a beam-column joint can be described by the moment-rotation diagram. The construction of the diagram allows determining the maximum moment that a connection can withstand and, consequently, the maximum relative rotation between the concurrent elements. The relationships between moments and rotations of a given connection represent its flexural stiffness.

The nonlinearity of the moment-rotation curve begins with the appearance of the first crack in the connection region. Figure 14 shows the curves of the bending moment as a function of rotation measured in the beam-column joint for the reinforced concrete (RC) and SFRC frames, for each of the analyzed configurations.

Figure 14. Moment-rotation curve of the beam-column joint: (a) $V_f = 1\%$ and (b) $V_f = 2\%$.

It is observed that the steel fibers increased the stiffness of the connection and, consequently, the bending moment. This increase occurs because the fibers delay the propagation of cracks, increasing the strength, ductility, and stiffness of the SFRC. It is also noted that a higher fiber volume provided an increase in the stiffness of the connection.

For the reinforced concrete frame, the maximum moment in the connection was 4.79 kN.m, while for the SFRC frames, F7 and F12, the maximum moments were 5.19 kN.m and 6.49 kN.m, for $V_f = 1\%$ and $V_f = 2\%$, respectively.

Regarding rotation, the reinforced concrete frame showed a rotation in the connection of 0.024 rad, while for the SFRC frames, F7 and F12, the rotations were 0.023 rad and 0.021 rad, for $V_f = 1\%$ and $V_f = 2\%$, respectively.

For the SFRC frames without longitudinal reinforcement in the beam, F1 and F8, there is an increase in the stiffness of the connection and, consequently, in the bending moment, compared to the reinforced concrete frame. However, the rotation capacity is very small, leading to failure for small rotation values. As the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam increases, there is an increase in the bending moment and rotation capacity of the frame joints. This demonstrates the need for minimum longitudinal reinforcement in SFRC beams.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to carry out a numerical analysis using the finite element method on steel fiber-reinforced concrete structures, which allows evaluating the influence of the addition of steel fibers on the moment redistribution and on the behavior of the beam.

Following the recommendation of the fib Model Code 2010 [5] for the numerical analysis of FRC, the modeling was carried out taking into account the pre-peak stage and the stress-strain constitutive law.

Based on the conducted analyses, it can be affirmed that the numerical models using the residual strengths predicted by the equations proposed by Venkateshwaran, Tan, and Li [19] were capable of representing the behavior of the SFRC, for concretes with a strength class of up to 45 MPa. The use of analytical models for the prediction of these parameters facilitates the design process of FRC structures, since the performance of experimental tests demands cost and execution time.

The numerical models using the CDP were able to accurately predict the experimental behavior, even with higher stiffness in the pre-peak branch, indicating that the model is suitable and has the potential to simulate the mechanical behavior of SFRC beams, while also considering the loss of stiffness with increasing load.

Based on the numerical modeling of the reinforced concrete frame tested experimentally by Cranston [23], a good convergence between numerical and experimental results was observed. Regarding the SFRC frame, based on the obtained results, it is concluded that the addition of steel fibers improved the mechanical properties and performance of concrete, providing post-cracking residual tensile strength, increased toughness, and ductility. The addition of steel fibers also allowed for the reduction of longitudinal reinforcement in the beam, decreasing congestion of reinforcements in the beam-column joint and offering better concreting conditions.

Upon analyzing the propagation of tensile damage in the matrix, it was observed that the addition of fibers caused a reduction in the cracking of the frame, attributed to the stress transfer bridging effect generated by the fibers.

From the analysis of the moment-rotation curve, it was observed that the steel fibers increased the stiffness of the connection, leading to a change in the moment redistribution. Therefore, the SFRC frame joints began to withstand a higher bending moment, and with a smaller rotation, compared to the reinforced concrete frame.

It was observed in the SFRC frames the need for a minimum longitudinal reinforcement in the beams. For the SFRC frames without longitudinal reinforcement in the beams, there was an increase in the stiffness of the connection compared to the reinforced concrete frame. However, the rotation capacity was very small, leading to failure at small rotation values. As the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam increased, an increase in the bending moment and rotation capacity of the frame joint was observed.

In the SFRC frame, the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam was also important for transferring stresses and moments from the beam to the column. In the analysis without longitudinal reinforcement in the beam, the beam-column joint functioned as a hinge. As the reinforcement in the beam-column joint increased, there was a dissipation of damage and a redistribution of stresses and moments.

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